

Enhancing Fault Identification in Photovoltaic Panels Using XGBoost

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ABSTRACT: Advances in thermal infrared imaging and image processing have enabled the development of fault diagnosis methods for photovoltaic (PV) panels that do not require the integration of expensive electrical detection circuitry. Processing of PV thermal images supports continuous monitoring of panels without disrupting operation and mitigates the challenges of manual inspection over large areas. Thermal images of PV panels are utilized to identify various fault types, including bypass diode faults, cell faults, open circuits, hot spots, polarization, cracking, corrosion, discoloration, and delamination. The proposed system employs the Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) algorithm to detect numerical characteristics from the captured thermal image variations, facilitating fault classification.

Keywords – XGBoost, Photovoltaic Panel, Hotspot, Delamination, Decoloration, Open circuit

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, photovoltaic (PV) technology and systems have experienced rapid growth worldwide. As a prestigious and environmentally friendly energy source, photovoltaic systems convert solar radiation from the sun into direct current electricity. The absorption of solar photons in a semiconductor releases higher-energy electrons that serve as the boundaries of the base crystals. An electric field must be present for the higher-energy electrons to exit the semiconductor and perform useful work once the free electrons are formed. Most solar cells employ a junction of materials with different electrical characteristics to provide the electric field. While conventional energy sources account for 85% of energy demand, non-conventional energy sources contribute 15% of electrical energy, with thermal and nuclear power plants making up the remaining 85%. Given that renewable power plants,

which account for 15% of total energy, experience some losses, it is crucial to maintain the plant properly. Among renewable energy sources, solar panels offer the highest efficiency in power production. Improving the precision and effectiveness of photovoltaic system fault diagnosis and detection can enhance the technique. Therefore, this work proposes an online fault diagnosis model for PV arrays based on the output current and voltage of the PV system and machine learning for a more economical and practical approach.

Common methods for PV fault detection can be categorized into physical detection methods, detection threshold model methods, and artificial intelligence diagnosis methods. Numerous machine learning (ML) techniques have been applied for PV fault diagnosis, including supervised extreme learning machine, trapezoidal network using support vector machine (SVM), probabilistic neural network (PNN), and decision tree (DT). The use of infrared thermography (IRT) for predictive maintenance and condition monitoring of electrical equipment has recently increased due to its inherent ability to identify issues without disrupting the system.

This study makes the following contributions: (i) applying gamma correction to enhance image contrast for improved distinction between abnormal and normal cells for better classification; (ii) developing a Hough transform peak detection (HTPD) algorithm; (iii) identifying optimal features for robust classification; and (iv) utilizing the Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) algorithm to support classification of various fault conditions.

2. SCOPE OF THIS RESEARCH

The primary objectives of this proposed project are to detect solar panel faults and prevent electrical power losses. Various defects can occur in solar panels, including delamination, discoloration, open circuits, hotspots, and others, leading to a decrease in system efficiency over time. Solar panel faults are mainly caused by dust, climate changes, and other issues. By using machine learning (XGBoost), images can be preprocessed under normal operating conditions. If any value changes occur due to issues, XGBoost can calculate the fault and capture an infrared thermography (IRT) image of the malfunctioning panel using an infrared camera. An XGBoost classifier can then be used to identify the fault and send the image to a designated station.

Faults in photovoltaic (PV) panels include hotspots, delamination, discoloration, and open circuits. Hotspots occur due to uneven heating, reducing efficiency. Delamination, the separation of layers, compromises structural integrity. Discoloration, often caused by UV exposure, impacts performance. Open circuits result from broken connections, leading to power output loss.

Hotspot:

Hotspots on solar panels refer to areas where the temperature is higher than the rest of the panel. They are unpredictable and can occur frequently. Cell temperatures can typically reach 150 degrees Celsius, resulting in irreversible and permanent damage such as glass shattering and cell degradation. When one cell is shaded, it reduces the overall current in the strings of solar cells connected in series, causing the healthy cells to produce high voltages and often reverse bias the faulty cell. The short circuit current of the defective cell approaches the hotspot operating current of the entire series string.

If the series string short circuits, the forward bias of the solar cell will reverse bias the shaded cell. Figure 1 illustrates that local overheating occurs due to the significant power dissipation in a small area, leading to reduced overall energy

production and efficiency of the panel. PV hotspots can be readily detected using infrared (IR) camera inspection

Figure 1: local overheating of solar cell

Discoloration:

Delamination refers to the damage to the lamination between the layers that compose a module. Delamination occurs when cells shift out of their typical cell connectivity. This leads to reduced heat dissipation, increasing the potential for reverse-bias cell heating. Furthermore, the high-temperature environment of the PV panel accelerates the aging process of the actual cell materials. Figure 2 illustrates that if discoloration occurs near the panel's edge, there is a greater likelihood of delamination.

Fig 2: Decolouration of solar cell

Delamination:

The yellowing of photovoltaic (PV) modules is caused by the degradation of ethyl vinyl acetate (EVA), a substance used as an encapsulant on the panels. Over time, this encapsulant optically degrades, changing from a clear state to a noticeable

yellow or even brown color. The yellowing and browning of the EVA encapsulant within the PV cells result in a color change from white to yellow and/or brown. This discoloration occurs when water and ultraviolet (UV) light interact with the encapsulant.

The discoloration of EVA leads to a difference in the amount of light entering the cells between the normal and damaged regions, ultimately causing a decrease in the amount of energy produced in the discolored areas. As illustrated in Figure 3, strong light absorption in the EVA film due to yellowing affects not only the aesthetics of the panel but also its performance and output.

Fig 3: Delamination of solar cell

Open circuit:

One type of persistent fault in photovoltaic (PV) modules is an open-circuit fault. When a major fault condition occurs, the bypass diode conducts to transfer electricity, rendering the entire PV string inactive. This state is referred to as an "open circuit." Compared to other arrays, the temperature of a PV module in an open-circuit condition rises significantly. Consequently, the open-circuit module array experiences an unavoidably high temperature. Figures show images of the PV panel's open-circuit fault.

3. IMPLEMENTATION OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

Sunlight hits the solar panels, generating solar electricity. Some materials produce electricity when

exposed to direct sunlight. This effect occurs when two thin layers of semiconductor material are combined. One layer has a depleted number of electrons. When sunlight hits this layer, it absorbs photons from the sunlight, causing electrons to become excited and jump to the other layer. This phenomenon creates a charge difference between the layers and results in a small potential difference. This combination of two semiconductor layers to produce electricity from sunlight is called a solar cell. Silicon is typically used as the semiconductor material in the manufacture of solar cells.

Fig 5:PV panel with IR Camera

To build a solar cell, silicon material is cut into very thin wafers. Some of these wafers are alloyed with additives. The doped and undoped wafers are then layered together to construct the solar cell. A metal strip is attached to the two outermost layers to collect the current. A single solar cell generates a very small amount of electricity.

To produce the desired electrical energy, the necessary number of such cells are connected to each other both in parallel and in series. Figure 5 shows that this arrangement is called a solar module or photovoltaic module (PV module). In a solar panel, the PV module is most important because it is very useful for generating electricity. However, the PV

module can be easily damaged or malfunction due to exposure to the open environment, which includes pollution, dust, snow, and other conditions. As a result, the efficiency decreases over time. To address this, an infrared (IR) camera is used to take a photo each time the color of the solar panel changes, and defects are calculated using XGBooster. Environmental conditions for thermographic measurements, such as temperature, solar radiation, and wind speed, are recorded before each capture. Thermal images are taken with a FLIR thermal camera.

IR images are taken with a thermal camera, and a temperature pixel matrix is obtained. Under normal conditions, temperature variation is constant. Using this method, defects in solar panels can be reduced, thus increasing the efficiency of the solar panel. However, with each fault, the temperature of the fault region increases. The increase in temperature is quite easy to capture in the IR image, which supports the detection of faults in PV panels.

4. XG BOOSTER

The basic idea of Integrated Learning (IL) is to repeatedly train several models and combine them into an effective and efficient integrated whole. XGBoost is an advanced ensemble method that provides better predictions with imbalanced class data. XGBoost is designed as a combined effort of boosting and gradient descent. In a reinforcement learning system, a series of repeated models is usually created and then added linearly to obtain the final integrated learner. When the weak prediction model of each step of the boosting algorithm is generated according to the direction of the gradient of the loss function, it is called gradient boosting, which can reduce the risk of overfitting and improve the generation of a weak learner. Unlike other methods, the XGBoost algorithm does not use a search method but directly uses the first derivative of the loss function. The XGBoost algorithm includes several classification steps.

For data with imbalanced classes, the boosting ensemble method XGBoost yields improved predictions. The XGBoost algorithm has multiple

classification phases. The XGBoost hyperparameters are first established. The dataset is then trained using 10-fold cross-validation based on the chosen characteristics. Various hyperparameters are tested, and the one that produces the highest Region of Convergence (ROC) is deemed the most appropriate. The third step is choosing the optimal evaluation model from the training dataset. The final stage involves using the evaluation metrics to obtain the results. Which offer several advantages such as

Ideal for datasets with imbalances: XGBoost is particularly effective when dealing with datasets where one class is significantly more frequent than the others (class imbalance). Its boosting technique focuses on improving the classification of the minority class, thereby addressing the imbalance issue.

Less expensive model in terms of fine-tuning hyperparameters: Compared to some other machine learning models, XGBoost tends to require less effort and computational resources for fine-tuning its hyperparameters. This can lead to faster model development and deployment.

Features an easy-to-use tree trimming technique: XGBoost includes a technique known as tree pruning or trimming, which helps prevent overfitting by removing parts of the tree that do not provide additional predictive power. This makes it easier to optimize the model's performance without sacrificing accuracy.

Quick and precise outcomes: XGBoost is known for its speed and efficiency in training and predicting. It can handle large datasets and complex relationships between variables, providing quick and accurate results, which is crucial in real-time or time-sensitive applications.

Minimizes mistakes: Due to its ability to handle complex datasets and its robustness against overfitting, XGBoost tends to make fewer mistakes or errors in prediction compared to other models. This can result in more reliable and trustworthy predictions in various applications.

Algorithm:

Extreme Gradient Boosting (XG Boost) has become a popular machine learning algorithm in recent years. It is an ensemble method that provides better predictions, especially with imbalanced-class data. XG Boost combines gradient descent and boosting techniques for improved performance. The algorithm involves several steps for classification:

Defining XG Boost hyperparameters: The first step is to define the hyperparameters for the XG Boost model.

Training the dataset: The next step is to train the dataset based on the selected features using 10-fold cross-validation. This helps ensure the model's robustness and generalizability.

Testing with different hyperparameters: The process is tested with different hyperparameters, and the set of hyperparameters that result in a high Region of Convergence (ROC) is chosen. This step helps optimize the model's performance.

Selecting the best evaluation model: The third step involves selecting the best evaluation model based on the training dataset. This helps ensure that the model is performing well and is suitable for the given dataset.

The XG Boost algorithm can also be used to retrieve the statistical characteristics of temperatures. Adjusting the parameters can further enhance the model's performance. Additionally, using a logarithmic loss function helps determine the number of decision trees needed for the model.

$$\sigma = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M y_{ij} \log(p_{ij})$$

Where , M - the number of categories
 y_{ij} - the real category of input data points and p_{ij} - the probability that the i^{th} data point belongs to the j^{th} class of XG Boost classifier.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This figure illustrates the accuracy of XGBoost compared to other boosting methods. The data points are taken at various stages and under different environmental conditions. Figures 6, 7, and 8 show that XGBoost consistently outperforms other boosting methods in terms of accuracy, regardless of the environmental conditions.

Fig 6: Analysis at stage 1

Fig 7: Analysis at stage 2

Fig 8: Analysis at stage 3

6. CONCLUSION

A problem-solving method based on the XGBoost classifier is proposed for photovoltaic (PV) arrays. The proposed model aims to detect common faults in PV arrays, including open circuit faults, line faults, local shadows, and degradation faults. These faults are simulated in Simulink, generating a large number of samples used to train and test the model.

Benchmark results indicate that XGBoost achieves higher accuracy compared to the Random Forest (RF) classifier. The diagnostic model's accuracy in Simulink simulations reaches 99.99%, while real-world test accuracy is slightly lower at 99.90%. Future work will focus on introducing feature reduction techniques to further enhance the model's performance by reducing computational complexity, thereby improving the PV fault diagnosis model.

FUTURE SCOPE

To improve fault detection accuracy in PV arrays, several strategies can be implemented:

Detect additional features: Identifying and incorporating additional features relevant to fault detection can enhance the model's accuracy. This may involve analyzing different aspects of the PV system, such as voltage, current, temperature, and environmental conditions, to extract more informative features.

Increase image contrast: Improving the contrast of images used in fault classification can help highlight relevant details and improve the accuracy of classification algorithms. This can be achieved through image processing techniques such as histogram equalization or adaptive contrast enhancement.

Utilize other optimization techniques: Besides XGBoost, other optimization techniques can be explored to further enhance the model's performance. This may include using different ensemble methods, such as AdaBoost or Gradient Boosting, or exploring deep learning techniques like Convolutional Neural

Networks (CNNs) for more complex feature extraction and fault detection.

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